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Synthesis of Some N¹(2'-Alkyl or Aryl-6',8'-Substituted Quinazolone-3'-yl Aminoacetyl)-N⁸-Aryl Ureas and Their *in vivo* Action on Caecal Amoebiasis of Rats

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VARIOUS quinazolones have been shown to exhibit appreciable *in vitro* amoebicidal activity against *E. histolytica*¹⁻³. Recently, a new pharmaceutical preparation containing a urea moiety has been claimed as a good *in vitro* amoebicide against *S. russeli*⁴. Moreover, the amoebicidal activity of the compound containing a CONH-COCH₂ group (in haloacetomides) has long been known⁵⁻⁶. Based on these considerations twenty four new N¹-(2'-alkyl or aryl-6',8'-substituted quinazolone-3'-yl amino acetyl)-N⁸-aryl ureas have been synthesised with a view to enhance the antiamoebic activity through the introduction of quinazolone moiety in aryl ureas. The results of these studies are presented in this communication.

Experimental

The title compounds were synthesised according to the route shown below.

N¹- α -Chloroacetyl-N⁸-aryl ureas⁷, 2-aryl-6,8-substituted benzoxazinones⁸ and 2-alkyl-6,8-substituted benzoxazinones⁹ were prepared by reported methods. Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

2-Alkyl/aryl-3-amino-6,8-substituted quinazolones: To the 2-alkyl/aryl-6,8-substituted benzoxazinone (0.01 mole), hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mole) was added and the mixture heated under reflux for 1 hr at 120-125°. The white fluffy mass obtained on cooling was recrystallised from methanol. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

N¹-(2'-Alkyl/aryl-6',8'-substituted quinazolone-3'-yl amino acetyl) N⁸-aryl ureas : A mixture of 2-alkyl/aryl-3-amino-6,8-substituted quinazolone (0.001 mole), N¹- α -chloro acetyl-N⁸-aryl ureas (0.001 mole) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.0015 mole) in anhydrous acetone (15 ml) was refluxed on a water bath under anhydrous conditions for 7-8 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the excess acetone distilled off. The solid so obtained was treated with boiling methanol and filtered immediately. The filtrate was concentrated and cooled for obtaining a solid product. The title compounds thus obtained after cooling were filtered and recrystallised from methanol (Table 2). The structure of the compounds was confirmed by the presence of characteristic ir spectral bands at 1720-1700 (C=O of amide), 3200-3100 (-NH-), 1680-1660 O=C of quinazolone) and 1600 (C=N) cm⁻¹.

Amoebicidal activity : *E. histolytica* (strain B-1) isolated from an acute case of human amoebiasis was used for the production of experimental caecal amoebiasis of rats. The amoebae were obtained in culture according to the method of Das and Singh in modified Boeck and Drbholav's medium with *Erchemichia coli* as a predominant bacterial associate.

Twenty one day old albino rats (Drackray strain) were used for these studies. The rats were prepared for infection by feeding them for 7 days on an autoclaved rice diet which has been found to produce consistent results in the production of caecal amoebiasis of rats.

The rats were inoculated with 0.2 ml of amoebic inoculum containing about 100,000 trophozoites of *E. histolytica* directly into the caecum by laparotomy (under ether anaesthesia) and the incision caused by suture. Infected rats were treated with the test compounds at a dose of 100 mg/kg orally once daily for five successive days.

The treated rats alongwith the untreated controls were scarified a day after the test administration and the presence or absence of amoebae in the caecal contents and in the mucosal scrapping determined through microscopic examination and culture methods and the gradation of infection determined.

Result

The results presented in Table 3 show the *in vivo* efficacy of compounds no. 3,7,17 and 22 (Table 2) on experimental caecal amoebiasis of rats. None of the test compounds exerted *in vivo* amoebicidal action on the trophozoite of *E. histolytica* in the

NOTES

TABLE 1—2-ALKYL/ARYL-3-AMINO-6,8-SUBSTITUTED QUINAZOLONE

Compound No.	X ¹	X ²	R	m.p. °C	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	Nitrogen % Found/(Calcd.)
1.	H	H	CH ₃	202	65	C ₉ H ₉ N ₂ O	24.43 (24.00)
2.	H	Br	CH ₃	230	62	C ₉ H ₈ N ₂ OBr	16.12 (16.53)
3.	Br	Br	CH ₃	241	58	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ OBr ₂	12.28 (12.61)
4.	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	152	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	17.47 (17.72)
5.	H	Br	C ₆ H ₅	158	75	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ OBr	13.64 (13.29)
6.	Br	Br	C ₆ H ₅	190	68	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OBr ₂	10.22 (10.63)

TABLE 2—N¹-(2'-ALKYL/ARYL 6',8'-SUBSTITUTED QUINAZOLONE-3'-YL AMINOACETYL)N²-ARYL UREAS

Compound No.	X ¹	X ²	R	Ar	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Nitrogen %	
							Found	Calcd.
1.	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	174	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	16.42	16.96
2.	H	Br	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	208	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ Br	14.2+	13.83
3.	Br	Br	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	218	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	11.68	11.96
4.	H	H	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	242	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	19.52	19.17
5.	H	Br	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	248	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂ Br	15.58	15.78
6.	Br	Br	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	226	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	13.24	13.68
7.	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	195	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	16.63	16.39
8.	H	Br	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	231	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ Br	13.53	13.83
9.	Br	Br	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	207	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	12.08	11.96
10.	H	H	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	189	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	19.49	19.17
11.	H	Br	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	199	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂ Br	16.09	15.78
12.	Br	Br	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	215	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	13.84	13.38
13.	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	162	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	16.28	16.02
14.	H	Br	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	182	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₄ Br	13.37	13.40
15.	Br	Br	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	212	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ Br ₂	11.54	11.48
16.	H	H	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	172	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	18.38	18.37
17.	H	Br	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	185	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄ Br	15.40	15.21
18.	Br	Br	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	217	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ Br ₂	13.04	12.98
19.	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	192	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	16.42	16.02
20.	H	Br	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	184	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₄ Br	13.88	13.40
21.	Br	Br	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	235	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ Br ₂	11.69	11.48
22.	H	H	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	160	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	18.63	18.37
23.	H	Br	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	174	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄ Br	15.38	15.21
24.	Br	Br	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	228	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ Br ₂	13.02	12.98

lumen of caecum or in caecal ulceration. No appreciable difference in the average caecal score of rats could be detected among those treated with the test compounds and those of untreated control. Emetine-HCl used as a reference drug, however, cleared amoebic infection from both the wall and contents from 6 out of 10 rats. However, amoebae could be isolated from the caecal contents of the rest of the animals with no detectable amoebae in the walls.

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TABLE 3—BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

Drug* code no. [table 2]	dose mg/kg	No. of rats survived treated	No. of rats clean infected	Average caecal score
3	100	3/3	0/3	4.6
7	100	2/3	0/3	5.0
17	100	3/3	0/3	6.0
22	100	3/3	0/3	4.6
emetine hydrochloride	4	10/10	6/10	2.0
untreated controls	—	10	—	7.2

* Numbers of the compounds are the same as in Table 2.